

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INVESTMENT PROSPECTS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

future of the development of the energy sector in Georgia belongs to renewable energies, which have a very significant potential. The renewable energy business has a clearly expressed financial and investment logic for Georgia, as it contributes to economic growth, investment attraction, diversification of energy sectors, the formation of a green economy and the implementation of ecological and climate ambitions. The paper aims to assess the investment potential of the development of the renewable energy business in Georgia and the assessment of investment projects and prospects in the context of local and international business opportunities.

Keywords: 1. Renewable energy; 2. Renewable energy business; 3. Investment potential; 4. Investment prospects; 5. Energy security.

Introduction: One of the main challenges for Georgia's economic and energy development is the availability of clean and cheap renewable energy, which is of crucial importance for Georgia. The energy business is the driving force of the state's economy and finances and is a necessary condition for the sustainable development of almost all sectors of the country's economy. The main impact of the energy business on economic growth is reflected in the creation of added value, job creation, and attraction of both local and foreign direct investment. Georgia's geographical location and potential make it possible to provide renewable energy not only throughout the country, but it also has great export potential.

Review and discussion: The energy sector of Georgia and, accordingly, the energy business have been experiencing significant progress in recent years, which is due to the trends of global energy transformation and the refinement of national policy and legislative regulations. The development of renewable energy business in Georgia is a key direction of strategic economic and energy change. According to statistical data, in 2024, the total generation capacity of Georgia exceeded 4745MW, of which 73.1% came from the hydropower business, 25.1% from thermal power plants, and at least 1.9% was the share of wind, solar and microgeneration. It is clear that the main source of renewable energy still remains the hydropower business. In addition, growing investments and activities are recorded in the solar and wind energy business sectors, although their share in total energy generation is still very small, which arises against the background of both technical and technological, as well as financial difficulties. Despite the fact that Georgia is a favorable region for the development of solar and wind energy businesses, due to the lack of investments, it is still not possible to achieve the appropriate scale, which is caused by the instability of state support and the low level of market development. The wind energy business sector, at the initial stage, provides prospects for both the diversification of energy supply and the development of

investment potential, as indicated by the already implemented and several ongoing projects. Among the challenges for the development of renewable energy businesses in Georgia, the low supply of solar and wind technologies is particularly striking. According to 2023 data, the installed capacity of solar energy was only 64 MW, and according to 2024 data, the installed capacity of solar energy is already 133 MW. The infrastructure in the wind direction is very limited, but despite this, the country's potential in this direction is also huge. In addition, from an economic point of view, the cost of installing solar and wind technologies has significantly decreased over the years: according to 2010 data, the installation of a 1 MW solar power plant was 5.3 million USD, by 2023 its cost had dropped to 800,000 USD, and today in Georgia this figure is approximately 445,000 USD. Accordingly, the price trend in the direction of storage systems was similar, which decreased from 2.51 million USD to 270,000 USD. This, in turn, increases the attractiveness of combined solar and storage projects. Several strategic directions have been identified that determine the successful development of the solar and wind energy business in Georgia: Improving the investment environment; Introducing innovative technologies; Integration of regional energy markets; Socio-economic consequences of introducing renewable energies; Implementing the principles of green economy and green energy.

Improving the investment climate and facilitating investment processes is one of the important factors in a developing economy like Georgia. Local investments may be insufficient in the renewable energy sector. Although attracting domestic investment strengthens economic and business activity and has an impact on productivity growth, foreign direct investment further expands the opportunities and potential in this sector.

In recent years, investments in the energy sector have been significantly high, but have been unstable over the years. The instability of foreign investment has been able to hinder the development of the sector, for which it is important and necessary to stimulate the

growth of foreign direct investment in the energy business, since its impact on economic growth is significant, which in turn is a priority for the state. A purposeful and predetermined policy plays an important role in the investment environment. Since 2022, about \$800 million in foreign investment has been made in the energy sector, equivalent to about 2 billion kWh of renewable energy. A significant achievement in the investment environment is the \$1.2 billion direct investment in the electricity sector between 2015 and 2023, which significantly increased installed capacity. Reforms implemented during the same period have helped attract additional investments in solar and wind. Also, the Black Sea underwater cable project, scheduled for completion in 2029, creates opportunities for energy exports and ensures integration with the European market.

In terms of improving the investment environment, it is important to note that significant legal and regulatory reforms were implemented in Georgia in 2022-2023, aimed at creating an attractive environment

for investments in the renewable energy sector. These include: the introduction of contract-for-delivery (CFD) auctions on energy carriers, a preferential tax regime for investors, and subsidies for launching new projects. These benefits have significantly increased investor interest and contributed to the strengthening of the market. The volume of investments in the renewable energy sector includes both state and private and international financial resources. According to 2023 data, the volume of investments in solar and wind energy business projects in Georgia alone amounts to approximately 150 million USD, and in hydroelectric power plants up to 200 million USD, which reflects the technical and infrastructure needs in the sector. Such investments are associated with both an increase in energy production and the creation of jobs and strengthening economic growth in the region. The main investment parameters of the renewable energy business and their growth trend in 2020-2024 look like this:

Table 1

The main investment parameters of the renewable energy business and their growth trend in 2020-2024.

Investment options	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Investments (million USD)	220	230	290	340	350
Number of projects	15	18	22	27	30
Jobs created	1200	1350	1500	1650	1800
Energy generation (GWh)	8700	8800	9000	9100	9200

International organizations and banks, such as the World Bank, the European Investment Bank and other international financial institutions, are actively involved in financing projects, which increases investment capital and promotes the process of technological renewal. The growth of investments in renewable energy businesses is associated with the introduction of new financial support mechanisms, such as state subsidies and an increase in private and international financial support, which creates greater market stability and promotes investor involvement, which in turn are necessary conditions for the development of renewable energy businesses.

Government policies and incentives play a major role in attracting investors. IRENA's Energy Transition Assessment 2025 assesses that prudent and flexible governance in the system, strengthening access to finance and addressing local needs are vital. In order to

ensure the growth of energy diversification, in parallel with the hydropower business, the state is obliged to promote the development of solar and wind energy businesses, which strategically ensures the country's energy security and strengthens the pace of economic growth.

In Georgia, investments in the development of renewable energy businesses are mainly focused on several areas: mass installation of solar panels, construction of wind power plants, rehabilitation of small hydropower plants and introduction of biomass use. In addition, the introduction of innovative technologies such as energy storage systems ensures an increase in the quality and reliability of energy supply, which is an important factor for investors. The analysis of investments in the renewable energy sector in 2020-2024 looks like this:

Table 2

Analysis of investments in the renewable energy sector in 2020-2024

Investment component	2020 (USD million)	2022 (USD million)	2024 (projected)
State budget	50	65	75
Private investments	120	160	200
International financial resources	100	140	170
Total investments	270	365	445

Despite the positive trends, the development of the renewable energy business in Georgia is accompanied by certain challenges, the solution of which is necessary for sustainable growth and large-scale attraction of investments. One of the main important challenges is financial risks, since the nuances related to the price of

energy and the dynamics of demand are always of interest to investors, especially against the background of ongoing changes in global markets. To overcome this problem, CFD auctions and state mechanisms provide certain guarantees and stability.

Conclusion

As a result of the economic analysis of the development of the renewable energy business and the discussion of investment prospects, the great potential and opportunities facing the Georgian energy sector are clearly evident. Economic models and investment analyses confirm that the renewable energy business, hydro, solar and wind energy, is a highly efficient and profitable business, in which the return on investment period is relatively short, and the rate of return is increasing. The main determinant of the sector's success is how quickly, innovatively, and stably the state and private sectors can maximize the existing potential, despite economic and financial risks.

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